

How Silent Are Silent Speech Interfaces?

Speech Reconstruction From Whispered and Silent Ultrasound Tongue Images

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Introduction

Evaluation

- We used an **ASR system** to calculate phonetic error rates (PER%) as a proxy for the **intelligibility** of the samples
- A traditional phone-level HMM/DNN system was used with a phone bigram

Motivation

- The final goal in articulation-to-speech direct synthesis is to **produce speech from silent articulation**
- Yet the recordings typically contain speech and articulatory movements recorded **in parallel**
- But what happens to synthesized speech, if the DNN model is evaluated on **silent or whispered** articulation?

Phonetic Error Rates

Speaking style	spk048	spk049	spk103
Original recording	21.6%	18.8%	19.5%
Normal (audible)	64.9%	64.8%	51.5%
Whispered	88.8%	86.0%	91.7%
Silent (hyperarticulated)	96.9%	89.6%	96.9%
Silent (normal articulation)	96.7%	96.0%	96.9%

- The **original** recordings show the error of the ASR system
- The **normal** recordings show the error of the 2D-CNN
- The 86–92% PER% shows a mismatch in the movement of the tongue and lips during normal and **whispered** speech
- The 96+% PER% values for the two types of **silent** recordings are even higher – except for spk049, where hyperarticulation led to a similar score as whispering

Data

- UTI and parallel speech recordings were used from three speakers (048, 049, 103)
- 200 sentences (~15 minutes) of (Hungarian) speech was used to train the CNN UTI-to-Mel networks with a 190–10 train-dev split
- In addition, the tale ‘The North Wind and the Sun’ (9 sentences) were read in four variations by each speaker (as test):

- Normal:** the sentences were read aloud
- Whispered:** The speakers read the sentences whispering
- Silent (hyperarticulation):** The sentences were read silently with articulation, moving the tongue and lips in an exaggerated manner.
- Silent (normal articulation):** The sentences were read silently with articulation. They were asked to retain from hyperarticulation.

Kymograms (left) and Mel-spectrograms (right) for a sentence read by spk103 in four variations

Recognized phonetic ratios

Speaking style	spk048	spk049	spk103
Original recording	100.9%	100.9%	100.3%
Normal (audible)	71.8%	64.8%	83.1%
Whispered	26.6%	32.8%	20.0%
Silent (hyperarticulated)	7.9%	29.5%	4.5%
Silent (normal articulation)	6.4%	11.9%	4.3%

- There were many deletion errors, probably due to the low volume
- We express the no. of phones recognized / real number of phones
- Even the **normal** recordings contain less phones (i.e. more silence) than the originals do
- The **whispered** ones have even less, i.e. less intense articulatory movements
- The **silent** ones contain almost exclusively silence, except spk049

Network structure

Ultrasound-to-speech direct synthesis

- A straightforward 2D-CNN architecture was used
- It processed one 64x128 ultrasound image as input, and produced one 80-dimensional Mel-spectrogram frame:

 - four convolutional layers (30–60–90–120 filters) (SiLU activation) with max-pooling after every second layer
 - one fully-connected layer (1000 neurons) (SiLU activation)
 - the output layer (80 neurons) (linear activation)

- Dropout layers were used after the 2nd, 4th and 5th layers

Recognized phonetic ratios

The generated Mel-spectrograms for spk103 (left) and spk049 (right)

- The Mel-spectrograms of the generated **whispered** recordings are similar to those generated for the normal recordings, but the timing is different and the formants are more blurred
- The **silent** recordings had quite low intensity for spk103 (for spk048 too) – this led to the ASR system to detect mostly silence...
- For spk049, the generated Mel spectrogram for **hyperarticulated silent** articulation was more similar to the whispered one – and so were the PER% values and the recognized phonetic ratios
- ...probably spk049 followed the instruction more precisely...
- The **duration** of the **hyperarticulated** recordings was in general larger than the duration of the other three recording types (for all three speakers)

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